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DECODING SALMONELLA ADHESINS: UNRAVELING MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS FOR NOVEL ANTI-INFECTION STRATEGIES

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Keywords: Adhesins, Salmonella, Bacterial Infection, Host-Glycans

Salmonellosis is a prevalent foodborne human health concern [1]. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, there are approximately 1.35 million reported cases of salmonellosis per year in the U.S., resulting in 26,500 hospitalizations and 420 deaths. The emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains and the economic burden derived from disease management necessitate the development of new therapeutic approaches targeting Salmonella [1].

The adhesion of Salmonella bacteria to host cells is crucial to initiate the infection process [1]. This step is ensured by the specific interaction between adhesins from the pathogen and receptors from the host cells, often involving glycans from glycoproteins [1]. Therefore, aiming to interrupt these interactions is a potential strategy towards preventing infection. In this regard, our objective is to study the atomic details of adhesin/glycan interactions, gaining insights into the rational design of adhesin-blocking glycomimetics.

This work focuses on the molecular recognition studies of adhesins from *S. enterica* Typhimurium, whose binding specificities have been partially described, particularly SiiE, StdD, and PefD adhesins. StdD binds to α 1,2-fucosylated glycans [2,3], Pef binds to the Lewis X blood group antigen [4], and SiiE binds to N-acetyl-glucosamine and/or α 2,3-linked sialic acid [5].

To discover new targets and tactics to obstruct the Salmonella infection process, our aim is to characterize the structure of Salmonella adhesins using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance techniques and study the recognition process of host glycans by these adhesins.

References

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Acknowledgements: The authors thank FCT-Portugal for the project 2022.06104.PTDC, 2023.00074.RESTART, EXPL/QUI-OUT/0069/2021, H. C. and F.M also thank the CEEC contracts (2020.03261.CEECIND and CEECINST/00042/2021 (UCIBIO-NOVA-FCT), respectively) and C.O.S. thanks to PhD grant 2022.11723.BD. UCIBIO projects (UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020), and Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy-i4HB project (LA/P/0140/2020). The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013-PINFRA/22161/2016, co-financed by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). The authors also acknowledge the GLYCOTwinning project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417 funded by European Commission.